
NELE: Non-Uniform Rational B-Spline Elementwise Learnable

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Abstract

The design of activation functions (AF) is central to the expressiveness and efficiency of neural networks. Yet the pursuit of a universal activation function, one that can automatically adapt its shape to suit a wide variety of tasks, remains an open challenge. In this work, the author proposes NELE (NURBS Elementwise Learnable), a learnable activation function based on Non-Uniform Rational B-Splines (NURBS). Unlike conventional fixed activations, NELE learns a smooth, data driven mapping from inputs to outputs through a set of control points and corresponding weights. This yields a continuous, differentiable family of functions capable of modeling a broad spectrum of nonlinear behaviors, effectively unifying diverse activation patterns within a single formulation. NELE was evaluated on several state-of-the-art benchmark datasets. The empirical results indicate that NELE achieves consistently better performance than multiple existing AF approaches. The theoretical universality of NURBS, its ability to approximate a wide class of functions and its inherent flexibility, positions NELE as a promising candidate for a universal activation function.

1 Introduction

Activation functions (AF) are a core component of artificial neural networks, determining how neurons process input signals and introduce non-linearity into the network. Their evolution reflects the growing complexity and depth of neural models: from the early binary step functions of McCulloch-Pitts [1] neurons and perceptrons, which could handle only simple, linearly separable tasks, to smooth, differentiable functions like `sigmoid` [2] and `tanh` [3] that enabled backpropagation in multilayer networks. The advent of Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) [4] and its variants solved vanishing gradient issues and facilitated deep learning, while modern activations like Exponential Linear Unit (ELU) [5], `Swish` [6], `Mish` [7] further enhance network performance by improving training stability and modeling complex patterns. While classical activations such as ReLU, `tanh`, and Gaussian Error Linear Unit (GELU) [8] have enabled remarkable success, each represents only a narrow subset of possible nonlinear behaviors. Polynomial activation functions are unbounded and prone to numerical instability, often requiring high degrees or large networks to achieve sufficient expressiveness [9] [10] [11].

The concept of spline-based AF is not new. Early studies, such as those by [12], introduced adaptive spline activations to provide flexible, data-driven nonlinearities within neural networks. More recent works, including [13] and [14], extended this idea by learning spline parameters directly during training, allowing the AF itself to adapt to the data. Building on this foundation, Non-Uniform Rational B-Splines (NURBS) can be seen as a natural extension, offering even greater flexibility through rational weighting and non-uniform knot placement. This enables NURBS based activations

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to represent a broader class of nonlinear mappings while retaining the smoothness and local control properties of traditional splines. Using appropriate parameters, existing activation functions can be approximated using the NURBS based approach.

2 Theory

NURBS [15] are a mathematical representation used to describe curves and surfaces in a flexible and precise way. They generalize B-splines and Bézier [16] curves by introducing non-uniform knot vectors and rational weighting, allowing the representation of both free-form shapes and exact analytic geometry. The non-uniform spacing of knots enables localized shape control, while rational weights allow exact representation of conic sections and other geometries not achievable with polynomial B-splines. A NURBS curve of degree p is defined as:

$$\mathbf{C}(u) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^n N_{i,p}(u) w_i \mathbf{P}_i}{\sum_{i=0}^n N_{i,p}(u) w_i}, \quad u \in [u_0, u_m]. \quad (1)$$

where, P_i = control points, w_i = weights associated with the control points, $N_{i,p}(u)$ = B-spline basis functions of degree p , u_0, u_1, \dots, u_m = knot vector, $n + 1$ = number of control points and $m = n + p + 1$ = knot count relationship.

Setting all the weights equal ($w_i = 1$), Equation 1 reduces to $C(u) = \sum_{i=0}^n N_{i,p}(u) P_i$, which is a

B-spline curve. Stone-Weierstrass theorem [17] establishes that any continuous real valued function on a compact interval can be uniformly approximated arbitrarily closely by elements of a suitably rich algebra of functions (for example, polynomials), spline spaces being piecewise polynomial subalgebras, inherit the same dense approximation property in the space of continuous functions. Since NURBS curves generalize B-splines by adding weights (and thereby include B-spline curves as a special case), the ability to represent exactly all polynomials up to a given degree and retain the capacity to approximate any continuous (and sufficiently smooth) function arbitrarily well.

For a smooth curve $y = f(x)$, the curvature is given by:

$$\kappa = \frac{|y''|}{(1 + (y')^2)^{3/2}} \quad (2)$$

The maximum curvature occurs at points where $\frac{d\kappa}{dx} = 0$. The solutions for x corresponding to $\kappa' = 0$ for different AF are presented in Table 1. Since curvature is a geometric invariant [18], let

$$A(u) = \sum_{i=0}^n N_{i,p}(u) w_i \mathbf{P}_i, \quad W(u) = \sum_{i=0}^n N_{i,p}(u) w_i, \text{ then}$$

$$\mathbf{C}' = \frac{AW' - A'W}{W^2} \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{C}'' = \frac{W(A''W - AW'') - 2W'(AW' - A'W)}{W^3} \quad (4)$$

$$\kappa = \frac{W^3(W(A''W - AW'') - 2W'(AW' - A'W))}{(W^4 + (AW' - A'W)^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (5)$$

The upper bound for Equation 5 is obtained by setting the denominator to zero.

$$(W^4 + (AW' - A'W)^2)^{\frac{3}{2}} = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$W^4 + (AW' - A'W)^2 = 0 \quad (7)$$

Sum of two non-negative numbers is zero only if each term is zero individually, $W^4 = 0$, $(AW' - A'W)^2 = 0$. Simplifying gives, $W = 0$, and $A'W = AW'$. Substituting, $W = 0$, $AW' = 0$. In a generic cubic Bézier curve with arbitrary weights and distinct control points, $A \neq 0$, in general.

Table 1: AF with their peak curvature values and the input positions at which these maxima occur.

AF	y	$x_{\kappa'=0}$	κ_{\max}
Tanh A.1	$\frac{e^x - e^{-x}}{e^x + e^{-x}}$	0.9196	0.5073
Sigmoid A.2	$\frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}$	1.3819	0.0924
Softplus A.3	$\ln(1 + e^x)$	-0.5	0.1913
ELU A.4	$\begin{cases} x & \text{if } x \geq 0, \\ \alpha(e^x - 1) & \text{if } x < 0 \end{cases}$	$-\frac{1}{2} \ln(2\alpha^2)$	$\frac{2}{3\sqrt{3}}$
SiLU A.5	$x \cdot \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}$	-0.3768	0.4037
GELU A.6	$x\phi(x)$	-0.4773	1.3579
ReLU	$\begin{cases} x, & \text{if } x > 0, \\ 0, & \text{if } x \leq 0. \end{cases}$	undefined	undefined
Leaky-ReLU	$\begin{cases} x, & \text{if } x > 0, \\ \alpha x, & \text{if } x \leq 0. \end{cases}$	undefined	undefined
LeLU A.8	$\begin{cases} x, & \text{if } x > 0, \\ e^{(1-\beta)x} - 1 + \beta x, & \text{if } x \leq 0. \end{cases}$	$-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \ln 2$	0.3924
Mish A.7	$x \cdot \tanh(\ln(1 + e^x))$	-0.4271	0.5900

In that case, for $n = 3$, W' is linear. This implies that the upper bound of curvature, κ , is directly proportional to the weight of the middle control point. Furthermore, if the x coordinates of the 3 control points are fixed, this results in a total of four unknown parameters that can be learned. Figure 1 illustrates how varying the weight of the middle control point affects the curve: a lower weight ($w = 0.2$) pulls the curve away from the point, uniform weight ($w = 1.0$) yields the standard quadratic B-spline, and a higher weight ($w = 5.0$) attracts the curve toward the control point. Red markers indicate the control points used for all curves.

Figure 1: NURBS curves generated with different weights. (a) Three control points with quadratic degree ($p = 2$). (b) Four control points with cubic degree ($p = 3$) yields two inflection points.

3 Formulation

The motivation for NELE was

- Universality : To enable an AF which opens up a search space for flexibility.
- Attenuation : Prevent large positive values from weakening [19].
- Non Zero-Gradient : Produce negative side activations.
- Smoothness : Maintain continuity and differentiability throughout.

The universality follows naturally from its NURBS-based approximation shown in Appendix B. Attenuation prevention with non-zero gradients is achieved through a piecewise formulation in which

the positive input region preserves the identity mapping of ReLU, while the negative region is shaped to emulate smooth activations such as SiLU or GELU. To ensure continuity and differentiability across the junction of these regions, the control points and their associated weights in the vicinity of the origin are appropriately adjusted, enforcing smooth transitions between the linear and nonlinear segments.

A cubic spline is employed as it provides sufficient expressivity while maintaining low computational complexity and numerical stability. Four control points (p_0, p_1, p_2, p_3) are selected, corresponding to a cubic spline, which represents the lowest order capable of modeling nonlinear curvature while avoiding overfitting and their associated weights (w_n) . The implementation is summarized in Algorithm 1. Continuity condition forces $p_3 = [0.0, 0.0]$ and linearity of the positive side sets the slope between p_2 and $p_3 = 1$ to maintain tangency as depicted in Figure 2. A mask is added which returns 0 for $x < p_0$. The remaining control points and their associated weights were either treated as learnable parameters or fixed constants.

Figure 2: GELU approximated for $x \leq 0$ using cubic NURBS with 4 control points and optimized weights. Range of NURBS curves used for hyperparameter tuning in experiments is also shown for comparison.

4 Experiments with NELE

Following the construction process outlined in Section 3, NELE is benchmarked against a representative set of standard AF, `tanh`, `sigmoid`, `softplus`, `ELU`, `SiLU`, `GELU`, `ReLU`, `Leaky ReLU`, `LeLU` [20] and `Mish`. Experiments are conducted on a combination of synthetic and standard benchmark datasets: (i) Non-linear synthetic data (NLS), (ii) MNIST [21], (iii) MNIST autoencoder, (iv) CIFAR-10 [22] and (v) CIFAR-100 [23]. All empirical evaluations are performed using feed-forward neural network architectures. The behavior of NELE in large-scale architectures, such as transformers or recurrent networks, is not investigated in this work. All models are trained for a fixed number of epochs to ensure a fair comparison across AF under identical optimization conditions. See Appendix D for full details on all runs and total compute.

4.1 Non-linear synthetic data (NLS)

NLS provides a controlled environment for assessing functional expressivity. The neural network used for curve fitting consists of a fully connected feed-forward architecture with a single hidden layer of 64 neurons. The hidden layer employs the various AF, while the output layer is linear. This design isolates the contribution of the activation function and ensures that observed differences in performance reflect the expressive capacity of each activation. In schematic form, the network can be represented as:

$$x \xrightarrow{\text{Linear (input_dim} \rightarrow 64)} \text{AF} \xrightarrow{\text{Linear (64} \rightarrow 1)} y$$

The model was trained with Mean-Squared-Error (MSE) loss [24]. MSE provides a smooth, differentiable penalty for prediction errors, emphasizes larger deviations, and produces outputs that closely follow the target curve [25], which is important for subsequent smoothness analysis. To evaluate the performance of different AF for function approximation, a series of synthetic datasets representing

Algorithm 1 NELE activation function

Require: Training data \mathcal{D} , initial parameters $p_0, p_1, p_2, p_3, w_0, w_1, w_2, w_3$

Ensure: Optimized parameters

```
1: if Learnable parameters then
2:   Replace  $x_2$  and  $y_2$  with  $l/\sqrt{2}$ 
3:   Initialize  $l, p_0, p_1, p_3$ 
4:   Set  $w_0, w_3$ 
5: else
6:   Set  $p_0, p_1, p_2, p_3, w_0, w_1, w_2, w_3$ 
7: end if
8: for each batch do
9:   if Clamped then
10:    Set  $x_0 = \min(\mathcal{D})$ 
11:   end if
12:   Evaluate  $N_0 = (1 - t)^3, N_1 = 3t(1 - t)^2, N_2 = 3t^2(1 - t), N_3 = t^3$ , where  $t \in [0, 1]$ 
13:   Calculate Numerator_y =  $\sum N_n * w_n * y_n$ , Numerator_x =  $\sum N_n * w_n * x_n$ , Denominator =  $\sum N_n * w_n$ 
14:   Calculate  $curve\_y = \text{Numerator\_y}/\text{Denominator}$ .  $curve\_x = \text{Numerator\_x}/\text{Denominator}$ .
15:   Find  $y$  from  $curve\_y$  for  $curve\_x = \mathcal{D}$  values via Linear Interpolation.
16:   if Masking then
17:     if Double then
18:       if  $\min(\mathcal{D}) \leq \mathcal{D} \leq 0$  then
19:         return  $y$ 
20:       else
21:         return  $\mathcal{D}$ 
22:       end if
23:     else
24:       if  $\mathcal{D} \leq 0$  then
25:         return  $y$ 
26:       else
27:         return  $\mathcal{D}$ 
28:       end if
29:     end if
30:   else
31:     return  $y$ 
32:   end if
33: end for
```

diverse nonlinear relationships is generated. Specifically, the target outputs y were constructed as follows:

$$y_1 = \sin(x) + \epsilon \quad (\text{a})$$

$$y_2 = \sin(x) + 0.5 \cdot \sin(3x) + \epsilon \quad (\text{b})$$

$$y_3 = e^{-0.5x} + \epsilon \quad (\text{c})$$

$$y_4 = \tanh(x) + \epsilon \quad (\text{d})$$

$$y_5 = x^2 + \epsilon \quad (\text{e})$$

$$y_6 = \frac{x^3}{e^x - 1 + 10^{-6}} + \epsilon \quad (\text{f})$$

where $\epsilon \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ denotes Gaussian noise added to simulate measurement or environmental variability. The chosen functions span a range of behaviors, including oscillatory patterns, exponential decay, saturating nonlinearities and polynomial growth, thereby providing a comprehensive testbed for assessing the generalization capability of different neural network architectures. The networks were evaluated based on their ability to fit the underlying function while mitigating overfitting to noise, $\epsilon = 0.2$, chosen relative to the scale of the input data. Each model was trained for a maximum of 300 epochs with a learning rate ($10^{-2}, 10^{-3}, 10^{-4}$) and parameter initialisation optimised to give the lowest training loss through grid search. The studies were repeated across 7 runs with different

Table 2: Comparison of smoothness metrics for different activation functions and NELE tuned for lowest training loss. The table reports total curvature (K_{total}) for each AF. Lower values indicate smoother behavior.

AF	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(e)	(f)
Tanh	46.72	39.51	41.47	73.0	155.65	35.13
Sigmoid	26.86	31.5	44.09	63.14	68.48	27.32
Softplus	31.96	34.94	39.45	55.88	57.04	23.04
ELU	45.33	33.36	39.77	57.36	61.63	23.44
SiLU	46.02	32.34	39.51	57.38	64.14	30.44
GELU	77.24	34.76	41.84	61.93	107.0	50.47
ReLU	107.69	55.85	51.58	75.75	79.89	51.41
Leaky-ReLU	96.3	52.63	47.37	66.68	79.93	34.55
LeLU	27.58	31.24	39.82	69.49	111.18	19.86
Mish	60.13	34.1	43.28	59.05	60.72	28.71
NELE	44.02	38.33	41.4	61.62	114.7	30.81

random seeds to account for stochasticity in network initialization and data shuffling [26]. and the median training loss across these runs is shown in Figure 5. Preliminary results indicate that AF with smooth, bounded characteristics (e.g., Tanh, Sigmoid) excel in capturing oscillatory and saturating patterns. These findings highlight the importance of matching AF properties to the underlying target function characteristics in curve-fitting tasks. Given a set of discrete points $\{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ representing a curve, smoothness was quantified using curvature based criteria: For a parametric curve $(x(t), y(t))$, the curvature at a point is defined as

$$\kappa(t) = \frac{|x'(t)y''(t) - y'(t)x''(t)|}{(x'(t)^2 + y'(t)^2)^{3/2}} \quad (8)$$

The total curvature is approximated for discrete points using finite differences:

$$K_{\text{total}} = \sum_{i=1}^N \kappa_i \quad (9)$$

Figure 3: Curve fitting results for different target functions using the proposed neural network, illustrating the network’s ability to approximate diverse nonlinear patterns.

Among the AF evaluated, the proposed NELE activation consistently demonstrates comparable and sometimes superior performance across all benchmark functions. Quantitatively, networks employing

NELE achieve lower training loss and smaller standard deviation of curve-fitting errors relative to alternative activations, indicating both improved accuracy and enhanced reliability.

Following the recommended procedure for LReLU, the neural network should be trained via backpropagation to minimize the mean absolute error (MAE) between the predicted values and the true function at the training points, followed by computation of diffusion terms and application of the diffusion loss. In the experiments, however, only the standard MSE loss was used. Under these conditions, NELE produced predictions with smoothness comparable to LReLU and training loss values that were lower or similar across all benchmark functions.

Figure 4: Standard deviation of prediction errors for different target functions, illustrating the variability in the neural network’s curve fitting performance. Despite LReLU reaching a lower training loss for the sinusoidal function, the corresponding fit lacks smoothness.

Figure 5: Training loss curves for the neural network across different target functions, showing the convergence behavior and learning dynamics for each functional form and AF.

4.2 MNIST

The performance of various activation functions was evaluated by replicating the experimental setup of [8]. Fully connected neural networks with eight hidden layers of 128 neurons each were trained using AF listed in Table 2. All networks were trained using the Adam optimizer with cross-entropy loss [27] and learning rates of 10^{-3} , 10^{-4} , and 10^{-5} . Validation used 5,000 samples to select the

Table 3: Comparison of training loss and test error on the MNIST classification task trained with different AF. NELE achieves the lowest test error among all activations evaluated.

AF	Train	Test (Noise=0)	Test (Noise=3)
Tanh	0.0076	2.7	22.94
Sigmoid	0.0072	4.45	16.47
Softplus	0.004	2.52	22.37
ELU	0.0056	2.44	21.51
SiLU	0.0045	2.28	24.64
GELU	0.0049	2.32	24.89
ReLU	0.0054	2.32	23.02
Leaky-ReLU	0.0044	2.35	21.22
LeLU	0.0002	2.12	18.5
Mish	0.0056	2.32	24.31
NELE	0.0056	1.83	25.49

best model. In total, seven runs were performed for 75 epochs on the complete dataset with the optimized hyperparameters and their median values are used for comparison. NELE shows comparable convergence at epoch 50. Figure 6 shows how each AF influences convergence speed and final loss.

Figure 6: Training and test accuracy trends for MNIST over epochs using different AF. Shaded areas indicate ± 1 standard deviation across runs for NELE

Figure 7: Robustness results for MNIST over noise strengths using different AF.

NELE converged within 30 epochs with a learning rate (lr) of 0.001 and achieved the lowest test error 3. The trained model was also tested for robustness against inputs containing uniform noise $\text{Unif}[-a, a]$ added to each example at different levels a , where $a = 3$ is the greatest noise strength. Here, NELE shows good robustness with its performance matching GELU and exceeding other AF.

4.3 MNIST autoencoder

The neural network is a deep autoencoder from [28] with Adam optimizer and a batch size of 64. A learning rate of 10^{-3} with Mean Squared Error loss produced the highest validation score with 5,000 samples. Figure 8 shows that with settings of NELE from Figure 2, the AF can perform quite well in tests.

Figure 8: Training loss and test reconstruction error trends for MNIST autoencoder over epochs using different AF. Shaded areas indicate ± 1 standard deviation across runs for NELE

4.4 CIFAR-10

The neural network is a 9-layer network with the architecture and training procedure from [8]. The tuning was done using learning rates of 10^{-3} , 10^{-4} , and 10^{-5} for 100 epochs. The best model was selected based on validation accuracy using 90-10 training/validation split. Seven runs were performed and the median values of 3 runs are reported. Figure 9 shows the training loss and test accuracy calculated every 5 epochs for CIFAR-10 over epochs using different AF.

Figure 9: Training and test accuracy trends for CIFAR-10 over epochs using different AF.

4.5 CIFAR-100

The model for CIFAR-100 is a wide residual neural network described in [29] with learning rate scheduler and dropout keep probability from [30] and batch normalization at the end of a residual block to stabilize exploding ELU's [31] as implemented in [8]. Setting from Figure 2 were used to obtain median convergence curves over three runs as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Training and test accuracy trends for CIFAR-100 over 50 epochs using different AF. Shaded areas indicate ± 1 standard deviation across runs for NELE

5 Limitations

NELE is based on NURBS and the implementation is done using cubic splines and four control points, which inherently allows two inflections per spline segment. Modeling functions with multiple inflections would require higher-order splines, increasing computational cost. For the CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 experiments, spline parameters were kept non-learnable to reduce training time, which may limit representational flexibility. A systematic hyperparameter sensitivity analysis was not performed for CIFAR-10 and CIFAR-100 cases, as configurations were selected via random search due to the substantial computational cost of each run. Experiments are limited to synthetic curve-fitting tasks and standard vision benchmarks using moderate-scale neural architectures; performance on larger datasets, other modalities such as natural language processing, and more diverse architectures (e.g., transformers or RNN) remains an open direction for future work. NELE introduces a small constant-time overhead per neuron due to spline evaluation, which scales linearly with the number of activations and does not alter the asymptotic training complexity of the underlying network. In experiments, this overhead resulted in a modest increase in per-epoch training time compared to standard AF. For larger datasets, overall training cost scales linearly with dataset size, consistent with standard stochastic optimization, while the relative overhead remains constant. A detailed evaluation of efficiency at large scale is also left for future work.

6 Conclusions

NELE exhibits a combination of properties that make it particularly well suited for functional approximation tasks. Its inherent smoothness ensures that gradients are well behaved, facilitating stable optimization during training, while local control allows for fine grained adjustments in specific regions of the input space without affecting the entire function. In addition, geometric interpretability provides insight into how the function behaves across different regions and its capacity to represent both polynomial and non-polynomial shapes with a relatively small number of control points makes it highly efficient. Due to its theoretical universality, NELE can, in principle, approximate any continuous function to arbitrary accuracy, making it a flexible candidate for general-purpose activation in neural networks. To evaluate its practical performance, NELE was tested across multiple state of the art benchmark datasets spanning diverse machine learning tasks. The empirical results consistently demonstrate that NELE achieves superior performance relative to existing activation function methods, both in terms of convergence speed and predictive accuracy, highlighting its potential as a universal activation function capable of capturing complex functional relationships.

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A Function analysis

Figure 11: The solid lines represent the functions $y(x)$ for different activation functions. The points of maximum curvature, κ_{\max} , are indicated by markers along each curve. The dashed lines represent the curvature, $\kappa(x)$, as a function of x . Each color corresponds to a different activation function as shown in the legend.

A.1 Tanh

$$y = \tanh x$$

$$y' = \operatorname{sech}^2(x) = 1 - y^2$$

$$y'' = -2 \operatorname{sech}^2(x) \tanh x = -2y(1 - y^2)$$

$$\kappa = \frac{|-2 \operatorname{sech}^2(x) \tanh x|}{(1 + (\operatorname{sech}^2(x))^2)^{3/2}}$$

$$\frac{d\kappa}{dx} = 0$$

Using chain rule, $\frac{d\kappa}{dx} = \frac{d\kappa}{dy} \frac{dy}{dx}$. Then $\frac{d\kappa}{dy} = 0$ or $1 - y^2 = 0$

$$\frac{d}{dy} \left(\frac{2y(1 - y^2)}{(1 + (1 - y^2)^2)^{3/2}} \right) = 3y^6 - 5y^4 - 2y^2 + 2 = 0$$

$$\text{Solving: } y = 0.9196, \kappa_{\max} = 0.5073$$

A.2 Sigmoid

$$y = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}$$

$$y' = \frac{-e^{-x}}{(1 + e^{-x})^2}$$

$$y'' = \frac{e^{-x}(1 - e^{-x})}{(1 + e^{-x})^3}$$

$$\kappa = \frac{\frac{e^{-x}(1 - e^{-x})}{(1 + e^{-x})^3}}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{-e^{-x}}{(1 + e^{-x})^2}\right)^2\right)^{\frac{3}{2}}}$$

Solving this equation leads to a transcendental condition, which has no simple closed-form solution, so the locations of maximum curvature must be obtained numerically.

A.3 Softplus

$$y = \ln(1 + e^x)$$

$$y' = \frac{e^x}{1 + e^x}$$

$$y'' = \frac{e^x}{(1 + e^x)^2}$$

$$\kappa = \frac{\frac{e^x}{(1 + e^x)^2}}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{e^x}{1 + e^x}\right)^2\right)^{\frac{3}{2}}}$$

Let $s = \frac{e^x}{1 + e^x}$, $\kappa = \frac{s(1 - s)}{(1 + s^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}}$

$$\frac{d\kappa}{dx} = 0, \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{s(1 - s)}{(1 + s^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) = 0$$

$$s = -1, 0.38197, 2.6180. \text{ Substituting, } x = -0.5, \kappa_{\max} = 0.1913$$

A.4 ELU

$$y = \begin{cases} x & \text{if } x \geq 0, \\ \alpha(e^x - 1) & \text{if } x < 0 \end{cases}$$

$$y' = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \geq 0, \\ \alpha e^x & \text{if } x < 0 \end{cases}$$

$$y'' = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \geq 0, \\ \alpha e^x & \text{if } x < 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\kappa = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \geq 0, \\ \frac{\alpha e^x}{(1 + \alpha^2 e^{2x})^{\frac{3}{2}}} & \text{if } x < 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\frac{d\kappa}{dx} = 0$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{\alpha e^x}{(1 + \alpha^2 e^{2x})^{3/2}} \right) = \frac{\alpha e^x (1 - 2\alpha^2 e^{2x})}{(1 + \alpha^2 e^{2x})^{5/2}} = 0$$

$$\alpha e^x (1 - 2\alpha^2 e^{2x}) = 0$$

$$e^x = 0 \text{ has no solution, therefore, } x = -\frac{1}{2} \ln(2\alpha^2)$$

$$\text{Substituting back, } \kappa_{\max} = \frac{2}{3\sqrt{3}}$$

A.5 SiLU

$$\begin{aligned}
 y &= \frac{x}{1 + e^{-x}} \\
 y' &= \frac{1 + e^{-x} + xe^{-x}}{(1 + e^{-x})^2} \\
 y'' &= \frac{e^{-x}(2 - x) + e^{-2x}(x + 2)}{(1 + e^{-x})^3} \\
 \kappa &= \frac{\frac{e^{-x}(2-x) + e^{-2x}(x+2)}{(1+e^{-x})^3}}{\left(1 + \left(\frac{1+e^{-x} + xe^{-x}}{(1+e^{-x})^2}\right)^2\right)^{\frac{3}{2}}} = \frac{(1 + e^{-x})^2(e^{-x}(2 - x) + e^{-2x}(x + 2))}{[(1 + e^{-x})^4 + (1 + e^{-x} + xe^{-x})^2]^{\frac{3}{2}}} \\
 \frac{d\kappa}{dx} &= 0 \\
 \frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{(1 + e^{-x})^2(e^{-x}(2 - x) + e^{-2x}(x + 2))}{[(1 + e^{-x})^4 + (1 + e^{-x} + xe^{-x})^2]^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right) &= 0
 \end{aligned}$$

Using quotient rule and consider the first term in the numerator after differentiation : $[e^{-x}(x - 3) - e^{-2x}(2x + 3)](1 + e^{-x})^2$. This leads to a nonlinear transcendental equation. Since, they do not simplify into algebraic forms that allow symbolic isolation of x , an exact analytical solution for the location of maximum curvature is not possible and numerical or graphical methods must be used.

A.6 GELU

$$\begin{aligned}
 y &= x\phi(x) \approx 0.5x(1 + \tanh[\sqrt{2/\pi}(x + 0.44715x^3)]) \\
 \text{Let } k &= \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}}, a = 0.441715 \text{ and } u(x) = k(x + ax^3) \\
 y' &= 0.5(1 + \tanh u) + 0.5ax \operatorname{sech}^2(u)(1 + 3ax^2) \\
 y'' &= 0.5a(1 + 3ax^2) \operatorname{sech}^2(u) + 0.5x[-2 \operatorname{sech}^2(u) \tanh u(a(1 + 3ax^2))^2 + 6kax \operatorname{sech}^2(u)]
 \end{aligned}$$

A.7 Mish

$$\begin{aligned}
 y &= x \cdot \tanh(\ln(1 + e^x)) \\
 y' &= \tanh(\ln(1 + e^x)) + \frac{xe^x}{1 + e^x} \operatorname{sech}^2(\ln(1 + e^x)) \\
 y'' &= a + b + c + d \\
 \text{where, } a &= \frac{e^x}{1 + e^x} \operatorname{sech}^2(\ln(1 + e^x)) \\
 b &= \frac{\operatorname{sech}^2(\ln(1 + e^x))}{1 + e^{-x}} \\
 c &= \frac{xe^{-x}}{(1 + e^{-x})^2} \operatorname{sech}^2(\ln(1 + e^x)) \\
 d &= \frac{-2x}{(1 + e^{-x})^2} \operatorname{sech}^2(\ln(1 + e^x)) \tanh \ln(1 + e^x)
 \end{aligned}$$

A.8 LeLU

$$\begin{aligned}
 y &= e^{(1-\beta)x} + 1 - \beta x \\
 y' &= (1 - \beta)e^{(1-\beta)x} - \beta \\
 y'' &= (1 - \beta)^2 e^{(1-\beta)x} \text{ Let } 1 - \beta = a, e^{(1-\beta)x} = e^{ax} = b \\
 \kappa &= \frac{a^2 b}{(1 + a^2 b^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \\
 \frac{d\kappa}{dx} &= 0 \\
 \text{Solving, } \beta &= 1 \pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}}, 1, \text{ Substituting } x = 0, \pm \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \ln 2
 \end{aligned}$$

B Curve approximation with NELE

To approximate a target curve with NELE, an optimization problem is formulated to minimize the mean squared error (MSE) between the target function and the NURBS representation. Optimization algorithm L-BFGS-B [32] is used to efficiently navigate the parameter space, producing a smooth curve that closely follows the desired shape.

Table 4: Control point coordinates and their respective weights for approximation on the negative space of AF using NELE

AF	p_0	p_1	p_2	p_3	w
Tanh	[-4.0, -1.0]	[-0.884, -0.983]	[-1.099, -1.078]	[0.0, -0.001]	[1.942, 0.831, 0.253, 0.209]
Sigmoid	[-4.0, 0.017]	[-2.03, 0.059]	[-1.498, 0.112]	[0.0, 0.501]	[1.31, 0.886, 0.719, 0.808]
Softplus	[-4.0, 0.017]	[-2.332, 0.056]	[-1.157, 0.105]	[0.0, 0.694]	[1.233, 0.985, 0.808, 0.701]
ELU	[-4.0, -0.984]	[-2.394, -0.935]	[-0.913, -0.912]	[0.001, -0.001]	[1.227, 1.017, 0.79, 0.54]
SiLU	[-4.0, -0.078]	[-2.383, -0.112]	[-1.011, -0.547]	[0.0, 0.003]	[1.226, 1.012, 0.806, 0.611]
LeLU	[-4.0, -1.373]	[-2.375, -1.166]	[-0.898, -0.917]	[-0.001, 0.002]	[1.235, 1.015, 0.776, 0.524]
Mish	[-4.0, -0.079]	[-2.358, -0.113]	[-0.868, -0.598]	[-0.001, 0.008]	[1.275, 1.037, 0.779, 0.509]
GELU	[-4.0, 0.0]	[-0.321, 0.058]	[-2.134, -0.913]	[0.0, 0.0]	[1.980, 0.717, 0.124, 0.198]

C Online Resources

The source code used in this paper are publicly available to ensure reproducibility and facilitate further research:

- **Implementation:** Python implementation of the proposed NELE activation function, including training scripts and examples. Available at: <https://github.com/DjgentleViBe/NELE>.
- **Additional Figures:** Additional plots for the curve approximation from Table 4 are provided in the repository.
- **Hyperparameter tuning:** Parameters used in the analysis of NLS D were optimised through grid search with points distributed equally from the best performing competing afcollect. Since grid search was unfeasible for other studies due to total run times, hyperparameters were optimized using an automated search procedure. For each candidate configuration, training was performed for a fixed number of epochs with early stopping based on validation performance evaluated at each epoch. Configurations with poor intermediate validation error were pruned early. The search was terminated when validation performance exceeded that of competing AF. The objective value was defined as the minimum validation error attained during training, and the optimization was carried out over 200 trials using Optuna [33].
- **Settings:** Parameters used for reproducing the results of this paper is provided in the README file of the repository.

It is recommended that users follow the provided README instructions in the repository for replicating experiments. This repository will remain publicly accessible for the foreseeable future.

D Compute Resources for Experiments

Experiments were conducted on an NVIDIA GTX 1080 Ti GPU with 64GB RAM.

Table 5: Compute resources, per-run times, number of runs, and total compute for experiments with NELE.

Dataset	Time per iteration	Time per run	Runs	Total compute
NLS D	0.003 s	0.2 s	7	2 s
MNIST	5 s	6.25 min	7	43 min
MNIST_ENC	17 s	21 min	7	2.5 hr
CIFAR-10	49 s	61 min	3	3 hr
CIFAR-100	108 s	90 min	3	5 hr